

Evaluation of Food Adulteration in Selected Indian Market Samples

Dr. Yogini A. Ranade¹, Rutuja B. Ghodechore¹, Diksha K. Shejwal¹, Rutuja N. Pada¹, Mahadev A. Jadhav², Kanchan M. Chavan¹

¹Dept of Biotechnology, Deogiri College, Chh, Sambhajinagar, MS. India.

²HOD, Dept of Biotechnology, Deogiri College, Chh, Sambhajinagar, MS. India.

Corresponding Author – Dr. Yogini A. Ranade

DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.20756873

Abstract:

Food adulteration is a common problem that affects the safety and quality of daily food items. This study was conducted to examine whether turmeric, chilli powder, and milk available in the market were pure or mixed with unwanted substances. Adulteration may occur when cheaper or harmful materials are added to increase profit, or due to poor hygiene, improper storage, and careless handling.

In this study, samples of turmeric, chilli powder, and milk were collected and properly labelled. Along with proper documentation and photography care was taken to ensure the samples remained unchanged during testing. Initially, the samples were examined for color, texture, smell, solubility, and visible impurities.

Simple qualitative laboratory tests were then performed based upon FSSI guidelines mostly for artificial colors, heavy metal salts starch, urea, detergent etc. The observations were recorded and compared with prescribed safety parameters. The results showed that a few samples were adulterated, while some were within safe limits.

Food adulteration is not only a health issue but also a social concern, affecting public trust and consumer rights. In India, unpacked and roadside food materials form a major part of the market and are not always strictly monitored. Therefore, affordable household testing kits can help consumers detect basic adulteration along with strong monitoring by regulatory agencies.

Keywords: Chilli Powder, Consumer Awareness, Food Adulteration, Food Safety, FSSAI, Iso, Qualitative tests, Milk, Turmeric, WHO.

Introduction:

Food is essential for human life providing the energy and nutrients required for growth, development, and proper functioning of the body (Whitney & Rolfes, 2018; FAO, 2016). A healthy diet supports immunity, maintains normal physiological processes, and helps prevent diseases (WHO, 2015; Gopalan et al., 2012). People consume a variety of foods such as cereals, fruits, vegetables, pulses, milk, and animal products to meet their nutritional needs.

A balanced diet comprises of macronutrients like carbohydrates, proteins, and

fats, along with micronutrients such as vitamins and minerals (FAO, 2016; WHO, 2015). While macronutrients provide energy and support body structure, micronutrients regulate metabolic functions and maintain overall health (Gibney et al., 2009). Therefore, the quality of food is as important as its nutritional value.

Food can be defined as any substance consumed to provide energy and nourishment. According to FSSAI, it includes all edible items, whether processed or unprocessed, along with beverages and ingredients used in preparation

(FSSAI, 2018; Codex Alimentarius Commission, 2003).

Food adulteration refers to the reduction in quality and purity of food by adding inferior or harmful substances or by removing essential components (Moore *et. al.*, 2012; Spink and Moyer, 2011). It has become a widespread issue due to increasing demand, economic pressure, and lack of awareness (Everstine *et. al.*, 2013; FAO, 2016).

There is a robust need to study food adulteration because it directly affects public health and consumer safety. Many adulterants, especially toxic ones like heavy metals or chemicals, can lead to long-term health issues such as organ damage and chronic diseases (WHO, 2015; WHO, 2020). In developing regions, where loose and unpackaged food is commonly sold, the risk of adulteration is even higher due to limited monitoring and regulation (FSSAI, 2018; FAO, 2016).

Adulterants can be intentional, such as adding water or artificial colors, or incidental, due to contamination during processing and storage (FAO, 2016; Codex Alimentarius Commission, 2003). Toxic adulterants can be harmful, while non-toxic adulterants mainly reduce food quality. Consumption of adulterated food may cause both short-term and long-term health effects, making it a serious concern (Singh and Gandhi, 2015; WHO, 2015).

The present study was carried out to detect common adulterants in widely consumed food items such as turmeric powder, chilli powder, and milk. Samples were collected from local markets and examined using simple qualitative tests based on standard guidelines (FSSAI, 2018; AOAC, 2019). Physical characteristics were first observed, followed by chemical tests to identify adulterants like starch, artificial colors, heavy metals, urea, and detergent.

The main aim of this study is to assess the presence of adulteration using simple and easily applicable methods and to create awareness among consumers (Spink & Moyer, 2011). By focusing on commonly used food items and basic testing techniques, the study highlights practical ways to identify adulteration at the consumer level.

Overall, food adulteration remains a major public health issue. There is a growing need for awareness, strict regulation, and simple detection methods (WHO, 2015; FAO, 2016). Studies like the present one play an important role in understanding the extent of adulteration and promoting safer food practices among the public.

Materials and Methods:

The present study was conducted as a qualitative analytical investigation aimed at detecting common adulterants in frequently consumed food items such as turmeric powder, chilli powder, and milk. A systematic workflow was followed, including sample collection, transportation, preliminary examination, chemical testing, and interpretation of results. Standard protocols were adopted and analytical grade chemicals were used to ensure reliability and reproducibility of findings (AOAC, 2019; FSSAI, 2018).

Sample Procurement, Documentation, and Transport:

Samples were collected from local markets in Chh. Sambhajinagar, including both packaged and loose sources, to represent commonly available products. Each sample was properly labelled with details such as source, date, and type. Photographs were taken at the time of collection to document physical appearance and packaging conditions. After procurement, samples were transported to the laboratory under controlled conditions to avoid contamination or

degradation. A Chain of Custody (CoC) record was maintained. (ISO, 2017, FSSAI, 2018; AOAC, 2019).

Organoleptic Characterization:

Initial evaluation involved organoleptic and physical examination of the samples. Parameters such as colour, odour, texture, and visible impurities were observed carefully. This step helped in identifying any obvious signs of adulteration and guided the selection of appropriate chemical tests (Ranganna, 2010, AOAC, 2019, Codex Alimentarius Commission, 2003).

Sample Preparation and Reagent Standardization:

Samples were prepared according to standard laboratory procedures. Solid samples like turmeric and chilli powder were homogenized, while milk samples were mixed thoroughly before testing. All reagents used were analytical-grade chemicals and standardized prior to analysis to ensure accuracy and consistency (AOAC, 2019, Skoog *et. al.*, 2014).

Qualitative Chemical Analysis:

Simple qualitative tests were performed to detect specific adulterants in each sample. Turmeric powder was tested for Metanil yellow using acid-based reactions, chilli powder was analysed for artificial dyes through solvent extraction, and milk samples were examined for starch using iodine solution and for dilution through standard tests. (Plates: 1, 2,3). All tests were performed under controlled laboratory conditions, and observations were recorded systematically (FSSAI, 2018, Codex Alimentarius Commission (2003)).

Observation, Interpretation, and Reporting:

During analysis, visible changes such as color development or precipitate formation were carefully noted. These observations were compared with standard reference outcomes to determine the presence or absence of adulterants.

The final results were compiled and presented in a structured format. Conclusions were drawn based on experimental findings, emphasizing the importance of food quality monitoring and consumer awareness in preventing adulteration (FSSAI, 2018, WHO, 2015).

Results and Discussion:

Sample Collection, Storage and Handling:

All the samples of turmeric, chilli powder, and milk were collected carefully from local markets in sealed condition. They were properly labeled and photographed for record (**Plate 1: Sample Collection and Documentation**). During transport, clean containers were used to avoid any contamination. Milk samples were kept refrigerated, while dry samples were stored in airtight containers. No spoilage or tampering was noticed, which ensured that the samples remained in good condition for analysis (FSSAI, 2018).

Preliminary Organoleptic Examination:

At the initial stage, samples were checked based on their color, smell, texture, and visible impurities (**Plate 2: Organoleptic Examination of Samples**). All samples looked normal and did not show any obvious signs of adulteration. However, after chemical testing, adulterants were detected. This shows that simple visual inspection is not always enough to identify adulteration. Similar observations have been reported earlier (Ranganna, 2010).

Turmeric Sample Analysis (T1–T5):

The turmeric samples showed noticeable adulteration. All samples tested positive for starch, which indicates that it is commonly added to increase quantity. Sample T2, T3, T5, were observed, positive for acetone, which indicates synthetic dye. Changes in solubility and appearance were seen in T2, T3, T4, and T5, and chalk powder was found in T2 (**Plate 3: Turmeric Adulteration Tests**). The differences seen in the reactions helped in identifying adulterated

samples. Similar findings have been reported by Everstine *et. al.* (2013). The presence of starch and chalk in turmeric samples as deliberate food fraud and substitution in spice products have been widely reported by Spink in 2011 and Moore *et. al.* in 2012). T2 was found to be the most adulterated in all samples.

Chilli Powder Analysis (C1–C3):

Chilli powder samples also showed signs of adulteration. Starch was found in all samples, and C1 and C2 showed abnormal results in solubility appearance tests. Lead was detected in sample C1, which is harmful to health (**Plate 4: Chilli Powder Tests**). The presence of lead may be due to contamination or use of artificial colors. Similar issues have been highlighted by WHO (2015). Sample C1 was the most unsafe among the chilli samples. In chilli powder, the presence of starch and lead indicates both intentional adulteration and possible contamination during processing. Similar findings reported in earlier studies further confirm that the use of artificial colorants and heavy metals in spices is a major food safety concern (Sharma and Rajput, 2018; Dhaka *et. al.*, 2019; Moore *et. al.*, 2012).

Milk Sample Analysis (M1–M3):

Milk samples showed different types of adulteration. Water was detected in M3, while starch was present in M1 and M3. Urea was found in M1, and detergent was detected in M1 and M3 (**Plate 5: Milk Adulteration Tests**). These results match earlier studies (Singh and Gandhi, 2015). M1 was the most adulterated sample, followed by M3.

Conclusions:

The study clearly shows that adulteration is present in tested food samples, may affecting both quality and safety. While some adulterants reduce nutritional value only, others such as lead, urea, and detergent pose serious health risks. Overall, the results highlight that food

adulteration remains a significant public health issue. Even simple qualitative tests were effective in detecting adulterants, emphasizing the need for greater consumer awareness and basic detection methods. Along with strict regulatory control, active participation from society is essential to promote safe and pure food practices.

The study also suggests future scope in developing simple household detection kits, which can serve as easy and practical tools for identifying adulteration at the domestic level. Such simple yet effective approaches can play an important role in improving food safety and protecting public health.

Acknowledgements:

The authors thankfully acknowledge the support and direction provided by the Principal, Deogiri College for facilitating and encouraging this work.

References:

1. AOAC. (2019). *Official Methods of Analysis* (21st ed.). AOAC International.
2. Codex Alimentarius Commission. (2003). *Codex General Principles of Food Hygiene*. FAO/WHO.
3. Dhaka, V., Gulia, N., Ahlawat, K. S., & Khatkar, B. S. (2019). Food adulteration and safety: A review. *International Journal of Chemical Studies*, 7(1), 1485–1492.
4. Everstine, K., Spink, J., & Kennedy, S. (2013). Economically motivated adulteration of food. *Journal of Food Protection*, 76(4), 723–735.
5. Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO). (2016). *Food safety and quality: Guidelines for strengthening national food control systems*. FAO.
6. Food Safety and Standards Authority of India (FSSAI). (2018). *Manual of Methods of Analysis of Foods*. Government of India.

7. International Organization for Standardization (ISO). (2017). *ISO/IEC 17025: General Requirements for the Competence of Testing and Calibration Laboratories*.
8. Moore, J. C., Spink, J., & Lipp, M. (2012). Development of a food fraud database. *Journal of Food Science*, 77(4), R118–R126.
9. Ranganna, S. (2010). *Handbook of Analysis and Quality Control for Fruit and Vegetable Products* (2nd ed.). Tata McGraw-Hill.
10. Sharma, A., & Rajput, Y. S. (2018). Detection of adulterants in spices: A review. *Journal of Food Science and Technology*, 55(7), 2529–2540.
11. Singh, P., & Gandhi, N. (2015). Milk preservatives and adulterants: Safety issues. *Food Reviews International*, 31(3), 236–261.
12. Spink, J., & Moyer, D. C. (2011). Defining the public health threat of food fraud. *Journal of Food Science*, 76(9), R157–R163.
13. World Health Organization (WHO). (2015). *Estimates of the Global Burden of Foodborne Diseases*. WHO Press.
14. World Health Organization (WHO). (2020). *Food safety: A public health priority*. WHO.
15. Whitney, E., & Rolfes, S. R. (2018). *Understanding Nutrition* (15th ed.). Cengage Learning.

Turmeric (*Curcuma longa*)

Chilli (*Capsicum annum*)

Milk

Plate 1: Tests results for Turmeric (*Curcuma longa*)

Fig no. 1 T

Fig no. 2 T

Fig no. 3 T

Fig no. 4 T

Figure No.	Test Performed	Type of Test	Observation	Inference
Fig. 1	Solubility & Appearance Test	Organoleptic / Physical Test	Cloudiness, turbidity, hydrophobic behavior	Indicates possible adulteration
Fig. 2	Starch Test	Chemical Test	Blue-black coloration	Presence of starch
Fig. 3	Alcohol-Acetone Test	Chemical Test	Disappearance of yellow color	Presence of synthetic dye
Fig. 4	Chalk Powder Test	Chemical Test	Bubble formation.	Presence of chalk powder (CaCO_3)

Plate 2: Test results for Chilli (*Capsicum annum*)

Fig no. 1 C

Fig no. 2 C

Fig no. 3 C

Fig no. 4 C

Figure No.	Test Performed	Type of Test	Observation	Inference
Fig. 1	Solubility & Appearance Test	Organoleptic/ Physical Test	Dull red color, sediment formation, bright red particles settling.	Suggests possible adulteration (synthetic color/ foreign matter).
Fig. 2	<u>Iodine Test</u> (Starch Detection)	Chemical Test	Blue-black coloration in all samples.	Indicates presence of starch.
Fig. 3	Lead acetate Test(lead salt detection)	Chemical Test	Yellow precipitate formed.	Indicate presence of lead.
Fig. 4	<u>Sulphuric acid test</u> (Lead confirmation)	Chemical Test	White precipitate is formed.	Confirms presence of lead.

Plate 3: Test results on Milk samples

Fig no. 1 M

Fig no. 2 M

Fig no. 3 M

Fig no. 4 M

Fig no. 5 M

Figure No.	Test Performed	Type of Test	Observation	Inference
Fig. 1	Flow character & Appearance Test	Organoleptic / Physical Test	Cloudy/clear solution with undissolved material, too diluted and highly flowable	Indicates insoluble impurities / adulteration with water
Fig. 2	Test for Starch	Chemical Test	Blue black colour observed.	Starch is present.
Fig. 3	Test for Urea	Chemical Test	Yellow color appeared	Indicates presence of urea adulteration
Fig. 4	Detection of cane sugar.	Chemical Test	Milk become curled formed.	Indicate presence of cane sugar.
Fig. 5	Test for detergent	Chemical Test	Violet purple color appear.	Detergent is present

Table 1: Detection of Adulterants in Food Samples (Turmeric, Chilli Powder, Milk)

Food Sample	Test Name	Procedure (Protocol)	Observation (Positive)	Inference	Reference
Chilli	Lead acetate	Dil. Nitric acid + Dil. Sulphuric acid added	White precipitate form.	Red lead salt present.	FSSAI, 2018
Chilli	Lead acetate	Dil. Nitric acid + Potassium Iodide added	Yellow persists/brightens	Lead chromate present	AOAC, 2019
Chilli	Starch Test	Added Iodine reagent	Blue/black colour	Starch present	FSSAI, 2018
Chilli	Solubility and appearance	Sprinkle a sample to glass of water and stir it.	Dull red color form.	Possible adulteration.	FSSAI, 2018
Chilli Powder	Brick Powder Test	Mixed with water, settled	Heavy particles settled	Brick powder/sand present	AOAC, 2019
Turmeric Powder	Starch Test	Added Iodine Reagent	Blue/black colour appear	Starch present	FSSAI, 2018
Turmeric powder	Solubility and appearance Test	Sprinkle a sample to glass of water and stir it.	Cloudiness, Turbidity, hydrophobic behaviour.	Possible adulteration	FSSAI, 2018
Turmeric Powder	Alcohol-acetone Test	Added to Alcohol/acetone	Disappearance of yellow color	Artificial dye present	FSSAI, 2018

Turmeric Powder	Chalk Test	Added dil.HCL	Effervescence	Chalk powder present.	Ranganna,2010
Milk	Starch Test	Added Iodine Reagent	Blue/black color	Starch present	FSSAI, 2018
Milk	Water Test	Drop on surface	Flows quickly	Water dilution present	Ranganna, 2010
Milk	Detergent Test	Shaken with water (Bromo cresol purple)	Persistent foam (violet color)	Detergent present	Singh, Gandhi, 2015,FSSAI, 2018
Milk	Urea Test	Added reagent (DMAB)	Yellow color	Urea present	FSSAI, 2018
Milk	Cane sugar Test	Added (HCL+ Resorcinol	Curdled form.	Cane sugar absent.	AOAC, 2019